

Making a math that was more (than rote work): Turn-of-the-century math education reform in the United States

Alyse Schneider, Oakland Technical High School, ✉ alyseschneider@berkeley.edu

Math education researchers have long advocated for progressive pedagogical methods centering students' active production of their own math learning. In this historical paper I reconsider progressive pedagogy in relation to teachers by locating it in the emerging research university of the turn-of-the-20th-century United States. As education and math professors developed research-oriented departments, they justified their extrication from teaching duties and other "rote" tasks through the ideal of the "active producer" of knowledge. And yet, despite professors' removal from the work of teaching, they sought to intervene on high school math teachers—who were presumably doing and enforcing "rote work"—with progressive pedagogy so that students could emulate the "active [university] producer."

Introduction

Mathematics education research has advocated progressive pedagogical practices focusing on student agency and activity—in contrast to "rote" and "mechanical" learning—since its very beginnings. While the effort to provide pedagogical recommendations based on student agency and activity is often portrayed as scientific and novel, these pedagogical recommendations are an almost 200-year-old tradition of education researchers, teacher educators and textbook writers, dating back in the United States to Samuel Read Hall's *Lectures on School-Keeping* (1830).

And yet, the emphasis on student agency and activity is widely held to have never been achieved in the "reality" of school mathematics apart from research, particularly amongst its proponents. According to mathematics education research, math teachers continue to deliver rote instruction in math. How do we explain the persistence of this tradition in the face of its reputation for failure?

Critiques of progressive pedagogical recommendations and math education research more generally have often explained the endurance of the "active child" and "math for all" as a case of researchers falling prey to capitalist ideologies or having an emotional attachment to reform. In this paper I focus on the material interests of university math and education researchers in maintaining their position as university experts. While "material interests" certainly includes salaries, here I focus on professors' interest in differentiating

Please cite as: Schneider, A. (2021). Making a math that was more (than rote work): Turn-of-the-century math education reform in the United States. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 3, pp. 908–916). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5416471>

their work from the work of grade school teachers. This is both rhetorical, in the sense that professors write about how their work is better than that of teachers, and literal, in that professors have an interest in not having to do the day-to-day work of public-school math teachers who teach children en masse.

Through a historical approach approximating “research on research” (Pais & Valero, 2012), I revisit the emergence of U.S. research universities in the second half of the 1800s. I argue that pedagogical progressivism in math education—as it was adopted by both mathematicians and education professors—was part of an effort to secure non-teaching jobs with expertise over teaching. The idea that researchers who don’t teach children know more about teaching than people who do was a historical achievement. Professors leveraged progressive pedagogical recommendations in constructing teachers as inevitably “rote” by nature of being teachers. They were thus in need of intervention from non-teachers who also happened to be the paragons of active knowledge production in the university.

Methods and theoretical perspectives

As a part of the broader social and sociopolitical turns in mathematics education (Lerman, 2000; Valero, 2004), critical mathematics education researchers have subjected mathematics education research itself to the critical gaze through “research on research” (Pais & Valero, 2012). This has included interrogations of school math and math education research’s participation in broader projects of white institutional control and white supremacy (Martin, 2013); imperialism (Bishop, 1990); settler colonialism (Gutiérrez, 2017) and capitalism (Pais, 2014). The ideal of the “active child” has come under critique for its inherent classism, sexism and ableism (Lubienski, 2000; Walkerdine, 1989; Yolcu, 2017), for being mythological (Valero, 2002), and for constituting a mechanism of control (Popkewitz, 2004).

Relationships between mathematics education researchers and teachers have received less critical attention. Chronaki (2004) and Darragh (2017) have argued that the gaze of the researcher maintains a sense of superiority to teachers and even colonizes teachers’ activities. Montecino and Valero (2017) take the approach of analysing how OECD and UNESCO discuss teachers, arguing that these discourses control teachers’ subjectivity. I take a similar approach by considering publications emanating from university professors, analysing how university professors portrayed their own work and that of teachers. I contextualize these portrayals in material shifts in the structure of university and grade school teaching.

My approach draws on the recent resurgence of historical research in mathematics education scholarship (Karp & Furinghetti, 2016). In particular, I build on the work of scholars using historical methods to re-consider math education research’s origins, goals, and role in broader political projects (e.g., Bullock, 2013; Lundin, 2012; Tröhler, 2013; Yolcu, 2017). I focus specifically on the turn of the 20th century because high school teachers’ and university researchers’ work had been relatively similar up until that time, but was rapidly differentiated, as I explain in the paper. As a case of the broader global expansion of public education and university systems, I consider the development of research universities in the

United States, specifically Johns Hopkins and the University of Chicago.¹ While the U.S. case is indeed a specific one, the focus on the evolution of a particular country's research institutions illuminates local relations between education systems in ways that are reflective of education systems around the world. In order to achieve this, my methodology involved drawing connections across relatively internal histories of turn of the century universities and grade schools. I also analysed key reports and publications relevant to mathematics education and, as a means of contextualizing mathematics education, drew from the literature on the growth of common schooling and normal schools across content areas.

As I show, as Johns Hopkins and then the University of Chicago established themselves as research institutions in the image of the German university, professors in mathematics and education alike were organizing for their own removal from teaching anyone but graduate students. These organizing efforts—as a part of a broader move against work that could be considered “rote”—occurred under the auspices of the academic ideal of the “active producer” of knowledge. It was in this context that mathematics and education professors recommended that students be made to emulate the “active producer” of knowledge as well. In pursuing “active production” and a larger distinction between their work and the work of teachers, professors portrayed grade school teachers as doing and enforcing “rote” work, particularly in their prescription of progressive methods emphasizing the child's agency and activity. As grade school teachers were increasingly subject to criticism from professors, they were also subject to the bureaucratization concomitant with the massive expansion of public school systems.

High school professors

In contrast to common (elementary) school teachers, American high school math teachers were an elite group until the late 1800s. High school attendance was reserved for an elite few, and high school teachers were often men trained at the university rather than women trained at normal schools. Labaree describes that in the case of Philadelphia's Central High School, teachers were originally referred to as “professor,” had dramatically larger salaries than common school teachers, and governed the school collectively without oversight (Labaree, 1986). While few high school teachers attended National Education Association (NEA) conferences, they were initially lumped into the “higher education” department with university professors.

Vice versa, the work of the university mathematician was more similar to that of the high school math teacher than it is today. University mathematicians were employed in their capacity for teaching rather than doing research (Roberts, 1997). Indeed, American mathematicians had yet to contribute substantially to the burgeoning European “pure” or modern mathematics scene, and most of the higher-level work was done for the military or by engineers. The category of “mathematician” was also larger and consisted of anyone who

¹ At the time, education in the United States consisted of common (elementary) schools, high schools and academies and normal schools for teacher training and universities.

practiced math regardless of their place of employment. This included teachers, applied math practitioners working for the federal government, amateurs and even hobbyists or “puzzlers” (Abrams, 2020).

That said, status differences between college professors and high school teachers—particularly those working in public schools rather than private academies—existed early on. High school teachers detected the “contempt with which many college men regarded high schools,” and “rarely asked professors to their meetings” in the NEA. Referring specifically to the 1870s and 1880s, NEA historian Wesley emphasizes that there was no “golden period in which public school people [teachers and administrators alike] gratefully accepted the educational leadership of college and university professors” (Wesley, 1957, p. 69).

To the degree that college mathematicians and high school teachers enjoyed similarities in their work, this would change in the last quarter of the nineteenth century. On the one hand, high schools were rapidly expanding, and thus high school teaching lost the status that came with scarcity. As the ranks of high school teachers grew, they became subject to the bureaucratization of school systems. On the other hand, U.S. mathematicians would come to focus on the production of their own, original research in emulation of mathematicians in Germany, France and Italy. New, “modern” or “pure” developments were increasingly abstract and removed from application, even as they took on the familiar “foundations” of mathematics in arithmetic and geometry. As the next section explores, U.S. mathematicians would begin to organize for relief from the relatively “rote” work of undergraduate teaching in favor of training graduate students and free time for research.

Inducting away from teaching

Johns Hopkins would serve as the eminent example of the new American research university until the mid-1890s. Johns Hopkins’ first president, Daniel Coit Gilman, who began his term in 1876, concerned himself with the development of postgraduate programs that would prepare one to do research. This demanded faculty equipped to train graduate students in the research process; requiring both proven capacity and the free time to keep up with new developments. Johns Hopkins trustee George William Brown argued that university faculty should “be teachers in the largest sense, that is, should have the ability and the leisure too, to add something by their writings and discoveries to the world’s stock of literature and science” (French, 1946, p. 7). Ultimately Gilman would relieve research faculty from the standard teaching assignment of fifteen to twenty hours a week. Adjuncts, assistants (to be pulled from the graduate students) and visiting professors would help provide undergraduate instruction (Parshall & Rowe, 1994, p. 57).

Gilman hired 61-year-old British algebraist James Joseph Sylvester for Johns Hopkins’ first professorship of mathematics on the basis of his research credentials. Amidst the increasing popularity of the experimental or “inductive” natural sciences conducted in the “laboratory,” Sylvester would argue that, despite the deductive presentation of mathematical research, the process of actively *doing* math was one of inducting generalizations from specific examples; it was experimental. Indeed, Sylvester’s approach to his famed work in

the Theory of Invariants depended on the extensive computation of examples. Ultimately he was able to hand off this relatively rote aspect of his work to dedicated graduate students (Parshall & Rowe, 1994, Chapters 2-3).

Sylvester was hired despite his poor teaching record with undergraduate students, and yet his record for inspiring mathematical producers was impeccable. Sylvester's first student, one of the very first research mathematicians trained in the U.S., would recall that "the professor broke every rule and canon of the Normal Schools and Pedagogy, yet was the most inspiring teacher conceivable" (Halsted, 1895, p. 206). Sylvester's lecturing style reflected the joys of mathematical invention; he would follow the train of any thought that came to him rather than teaching a curriculum. He would have students work on open problems toward the goal of presenting "laboratory reports." (Parshall and Rowe, 1994, p. 86). In short, Sylvester taught his students to "*do* mathematics actively, not merely study it passively" ... they had to "get their hands dirty" (Parshall and Rowe, 1994, pp. 82, 106).

Under Gilman's leadership and in Sylvester's mathematics department, the role of the university professor was reimagined as first and foremost the role of the "active producer," and their most important instructional role was to facilitate future mathematicians in embodying it. Sylvester's first student explains Sylvester's belief that "without unceasing original research and published original work there could be no real university teaching, and that any university professor who, without such a basis, pretended to be a good teacher, was, consciously or unconsciously, a selfish fraud" (Halsted, 1895, p. 204).

Across the next ten years, American mathematicians would increasingly follow in the footsteps of their European counterparts in their focus on "pure mathematics," abstract and apart from application. In 1888, the founding of the American Mathematical Society –in emulation of the London Mathematical Society– formalized the collective interests of U.S. university mathematicians in focusing on pure research, rather than teaching or application. And yet, university mathematicians would not hesitate to make recommendations to grade school education, despite their ever-increasing removal from it.

High schools were expanding astronomically in the United States. While there were 325 high schools in 1860, by 1890 there were approximately 2,536. In contrast to the college prep academies tied to the colleges by entrance exams, the new high schools had started relatively beholden to the (largely job-training) needs of the communities that they were located in (Wesley, 1957, pp. 64–66). Concerned about the development of the high schools outside of their control, the National Education Association assembled a committee consisting mainly of college professors and private school principals in order to administer organization to the burgeoning array of secondary school options.

The process of generating what would ultimately be the Committee of Ten Report quickly extended out of the typical terrain of curriculum recommendations and into pedagogy. Under the leadership of Sylvester's successor at Johns Hopkins, Simon Newcomb, the Math Committee of the Committee of Ten recommended increased abstraction in arithmetic as a means of avoiding learning myriad rote procedures (NEA, 1894). For example, applied work

in “commercial mathematics” was rejected for relying excessively on rote learning. And yet, it was also recommended that abstractions be motivated “inductively” through concrete examples.

To conclude, math professors, within the broader emergence of the U.S. research university, were increasingly organizing for time for “pure” research devoid of rote computation. The new ethic of the “active producer,” who taught by example and collaboration, was developed in contrast to the relatively “rote” work of teaching the canon. Even as math professors became more removed from teaching anyone who was not training to be a math professor themselves, they sought to extend the reach of the “active producer” ideal and avoidance of rote work to grade school math education.

Finding the foundation

The ideal of the student as an active producer, in the image of the new university researchers, was also institutionalized through the newly developing chairs and departments of pedagogy. John Dewey famously embraced students’ self-directed learning in activity, which he conceptualized in contrast to teacher-directed, and thus rote, schoolwork. Dewey arrived at the re-established and Rockefeller-financed University of Chicago in 1894. The university’s president was gearing Chicago to overtake Johns Hopkins as the premier U.S. research university. At the same time, he sought to expand the reaches of the university into teacher education (which was still largely undertaken at normal schools) and the operations of the Chicago public school district. Dewey was just the person to help.

As head of the departments of philosophy and pedagogy, Dewey argued that the best way to avoid students doing rote work was for education professors to engage in an academic search for the “foundations” of education; psychologically, historically, and sociologically. However, rather than experimentation, this involved applying a pseudo-historical, racist theory of human progress (Fallace, 2009). Dewey gave central importance to students re-enacting the “stages of civilization.” In order to re-enact these stages, students were to engage in historic manual occupations toward active re-discovery of concepts within the context of work. By revisiting the supposed social and economic foundations of civilization, the study of education would take content “out of the abstractness forced upon it for purposes of its own convenience of study and put into its concrete connections with the rest of the world” (Dewey, 1986, p. 287). Ironically, this project of taking content out of “forced” abstractness would be led by professors—who traded in abstractions—rather than teachers.

In asserting theoretical foundations as a privileged means of educational improvement, Dewey, among other university professors who did not work in grade school education, asserted themselves as having improved knowledge of how to teach over teachers themselves. Indeed, as Dewey declared, “without insight into the psychological structure and activities of the individual, the educative process will, therefore, be haphazard and arbitrary” (Dewey, 1897, p. 85). In the current state of education “far too much of the stimulus and control proceeds from the teacher, because of neglect of the idea of the school as a form of social life” (p. 88). In practice, progressive pedagogy’s orientation around “foundations” relocated

the locus of educational knowledge from the teacher to the university, which Dewey argued at length was the correct location for such investigation (Dewey, 1896).

The active producers

Leadership of the U.S. mathematics community also migrated from Johns Hopkins to the University of Chicago under department head Eliakim Hastings Moore. The Chicago department aggressively pursued pure mathematics, ironically reaching new heights of abstraction through a focus on the very “foundations” of mathematics, including arithmetic and geometry. Indeed, mathematicians at the University of Chicago had ceased to think of the mathematicians of the prior generation, who had pursued applied work in fields such as astronomy, as mathematicians at all (Roberts, 1997, p. 112). Professors were lured to Chicago with the understanding that they would work exclusively in the graduate school and not take on undergraduate teaching responsibilities (Boyer, 2015, p. 81). Applications and undergraduate teaching fell under the category of rote work and were not conducive to “active production.”

American mathematicians engaging in pure mathematics became absorbed in the axiomatic description of systems (such as geometry or arithmetic) or objects (such as a group). For example, instead of thinking of the integers as the relatively concrete list of numbers {...-2, -1, 0, 1, 2}, they could be reconsidered as a particular case of an abstract group, to be defined by a minimal and independent number of relations between its elements rather than by what those elements are. In this they owed to the work of European mathematicians such as David Hilbert and Felix Klein, who had trained much of the University of Chicago’s math department. And yet, American mathematicians took this to a new extreme, seeking to cleanse their systematizations from relatively concrete mathematical “objects” in favor of their abstract properties (Moore, 1903).

As Moore’s math department purged themselves of the concrete as a means of becoming active producers, Moore took up arms for mathematics education reforms promising to facilitate students in doing the same. This was, however, through the opposite approach of engaging students in the concrete. In his famed exiting speech as president of the American Mathematical Society, “On the foundations of mathematics,” Moore advocated for the laboratory method and correlation between math and science as a means of engaging students in “the practical sides of mathematics.” He also recommended the “diminution of emphasis on the systematic and formal sides of mathematics”; students should study “the subject itself, and not the words, either printed or oral, of any authority on the subject” (Moore, 1903, pp. 405, 419). Students would learn to “be sure in a naïve and elementary way,” and mathematics education would then be imbued with the “spirit of research (pp. 406, 411). Rather than learning through the direct instruction of the teacher, “in most cases, much of the proof should be secured by the research work of the students themselves” (p. 419).

Conundrums

In this paper, I demonstrated that rather than being a natural state of affairs, current relations between teachers and mathematics education professors (and the professoriate more generally) are a historical achievement, in which progressive pedagogy played a large role. Progressive pedagogy portrays not only an ideal for children’s “active learning, but also emulates university researchers’ self-image and fight for work conditions in juxtaposition to the “rote” situation of teachers. Professors argued that, by nature of not being teachers, they knew more about teaching than teachers, because they were liberated from the presumed “rote”-ness of being a teacher. Ironically, they also recommended that teachers leverage the concrete as a privileged means for students to become active producers, even as they retreated increasingly into the abstract themselves.

Rather than being a problem that can be solved by improved theoretical perspectives, I would argue that the researchers’ “colonizing gaze” on the teacher is a constituent part of the structure and material conditions of university teacher education and mathematics education research. More work is needed in understanding the relationship between researchers and teachers through the perspective of work conditions and class relations. This includes questions of how we portray teachers and researchers as differentially able to reflect and know about teaching, which has consequences for who gets paid to take free time for reflection. This in turn has consequences for the improvement of teaching.

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